

Soil and crop management

Effect of dipping rice roots in phosphate nutrient solutions on grain yield

Y. Yogeswara Rao, Mohd. Ikranullah, and L. G. Giri Rao, Students' Farm, Rajendranagar, Hyderabad, India

Roots of rice seedlings were dipped in phosphate nutrient solutions of potassium dihydrogen phosphate (KH₂PO₄), monoammonium phosphate (MAP), urea ammonium phosphate (UAP), and ammonium nitro phosphate (ANP) with and without soil application of P₂O₅ in field experiments at Rajendranagar, Hyderabad, India, during rabi 1975 and 1976. The treatments were in a randomized block design with four replications.

The roots were kept for 10 minutes in phosphatic fertilizer solution before transplanting.

Yield differences were significant in both years. Application of only nitrogen and potassium without P₂O₅ gave a very low yield (3.9 t/ha), showing the rice crop's need for P₂O₅. The control (no manure) had the lowest grain yield. The differences in grain yield among treatments with KH₂PO₄, MAP, UAP, and ANP 2% solution were not significant, indicating that treating rice seedlings with any of the solutions will be equally beneficial.

Dipping roots of seedlings in phosphate solutions did not fully compensate for the phosphorus supplied through soil application of 60 kg P₂O₅/ha. When 30

kg P₂O₅/ha was applied in addition to seedling treatment with 2% solutions, grain yield was higher than when seedlings were dipped in 2% solutions without 30 kg P₂O₅/ha, but equal to yield with soil application of 60 kg P₂O₅/ha.

Net returns were maximum with 100 N, 30 P₂O₅, 30 K₂O kg/ha + root dipping in 2% ANP (\$291/ha) and with 100 N, 30 P₂O₅, 30 K₂O kg/ha + root dipping in 2% UAP (\$280/ha), which registered an increase in net return of \$49/ha and \$38/ha over 100 N, 60 P₂O₅, and 30 kg K₂O kg/ha treatment.

It appears that dipping roots in a 2% solution of ANP or UAP plus soil application of 30 kg/ha P₂O₅/ha was more profitable than soil application of 60 kg P₂O₅/ha alone. ■

Groundwater and vegetative growth, yield components, and evapotranspiration demand of dryland rice

Tapan Ghosh, K. C. Sharma, and G. L. Sharma, Agronomy Department, G. B. Pant University of Agriculture and Technology, Pantnagar, U.P. (India)

A 1980-81 field experiment at Pantnagar, India, investigated the contribution of groundwater to vegetative growth, yield components, and evapotranspiration demand (ET) of dryland

rice. Groundwater contribution was estimated as the difference in ET for polyethylene-lined and unlined plots. ET was varied by applying irrigations at 25%, 50%, and 75% moisture depletion from field capacity.

At maturity, significant differences in growth parameters occurred among treatments (see table). Significantly greater numbers of panicles were observed when groundwater contribution was high — 25% available soil moisture depletion from 0-30, 30-60, and

60-90 cm depths. Other yield attributes also were maximum under the wetter regime (25% moisture depletion) than under drier regimes (50% and 75% moisture depletion). Total dry matter (grain and straw) was maximum when irrigation was applied at depletion of 25% available moisture at 30-60 cm depth. That showed a groundwater contribution of 108 cm (see table). Yield attributes and yield decreased when the contribution of groundwater was low (50% and 75% moisture depletion treatments).

Estimates of the contribution of groundwater to total evapotranspiration (ET) and the effect on growth, yield, and yield components of dryland rice (Cv UPR82-1), 1980 in Pantnagar, India.

Treatment (% moisture depletion from field capacity at particular soil depth)	ET under lined plot (cm)	ET under unlined plot (cm)	Groundwater contribution (cm)	Growth parameters at maturity		Yield components				
				Crop density (no. of shoots/m row length)	Crop height (cm)	Panicles (no./m row length)	Grain wt (g/panicle)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Total dry matter (t/ha)	
25%	0-30 cm	402	249	153	177	66	71	1.83	4.0	8.4
	30-60 cm	277	169	108	167	67	68	1.89	4.1	8.8
	60-90 cm	183	132	51	164	73	66	1.79	3.6	7.8
50%	0-30 cm	267	169	69	150	66	64	1.78	3.5	7.1
	30-60 cm	202	156	46	141	59	57	1.78	3.5	7.7
	60-90 cm	154	131	23	134	65	58	1.77	3.2	6.8
75%	0-30 cm	248	229	18	106	59	56	1.74	2.9	6.3
	30-60 cm	190	165	24	100	62	55	1.66	2.9	6.1
	60-90 cm	163	150	13	86	64	55	1.64	2.7	5.7
F test					Significant	Significant	Significant	Nonsignificant	Significant	Significant
C.D. at 5%					14.0	1.4	3.0	—	0.5	1.4

The contribution of groundwater to total ET was maximum when plants were irrigated at 25% available soil moisture depletion at 0-30 cm depth. In drier regimes, the rice plant failed to extract moisture from the groundwater table, although the gradient of water potential was maximum. Liquid phase continuity was disturbed under the drier soil regimes, reducing groundwater contribution to a minimum. ■

Response of rice varieties to nitrogen manuring at Tirur, India

S. Nazeer Peeran and B. V. Anandam, Soil Science Section, Paddy Experiment Station, Tirur 602025, Chingleput District, Tamil Nadu, India

A field trial during *sornavari* 1980 (May-June to August-September) stu-

Grain yields (t/ha) of 6 rices treated with 5 nitrogen levels at Tirur, India.

Varieties	Grain yield (t/ha)					Mean	Fertilizer index
	No N	40kg N/ha	80 kg N/ha	120kg N/ha	160 kg N/ha		
AS1374	3.1	3.9	4.4	5.5 ^a	4.9	4.3	1.3
TM3207	2.8	3.4	4.0	4.3	4.7 ^a	3.8	1.2
TM2871	2.9	3.8	3.8	4.4	5.0 ^a	4.0	1.3
TM2048	2.8	3.2	3.8	4.1	4.3 ^a	3.1	1.2
TM1898	3.2	3.8	4.8	5.0	5.6 ^a	4.5	1.3
TKM9	3.6	4.0	5.0	5.6 ^a	5.5	4.7	1.2
Mean	3.1	3.7	4.3	4.8	5.0		
				F-test	SE	CD	
Variety				S**	0.095	0.541	
N levels				S**	0.053	0.345	
Interactions:							
				N level × variety	S**	0.088	0.347
				Variety × N level	S**	0.103	0.561

^a Highest optimum yields. **Significant at 0.99 level.

died the yield potential of pre-release cultures under different levels of nitrogen fertilizer (N). Six rice varieties and five N levels were tested in a split-plot design replicated twice (see table).

Yield differences were statistically significant for the interaction of nitrogen levels and rice varieties. TKM9 had the highest yield at all N levels of treatment, but had low response to N. ■

Contribution of seedling quality to rice production

S. A. Sattar, Harun-Ar-Rashid, and A. J. M. A. Islam, Bangladesh Rice Research Institute (BRRI)

The contribution of seedling quality to grain yield and growth duration of transplanted rice was studied in the cold, dry, and wet seasons. High quality seedlings were produced by giving better management in the nursery; poor qual-

ity ones were obtained from a poorly managed nursery. A physical seedling quality index (SQI) was calculated (Table 1) and used for correlation analysis with yield, growth duration, and seedling strength measured in milligrams of dry matter produced per centimeter length of seedling.

The SQI correlated strongly with seedling strength (Table 2). SQ had no influence on grain yield and was negatively associated with growth duration. But high quality seedlings shortened crop growth duration by at least 6-10 days. ■

Table 1. Sample calculation of the physical quality index for rice seedlings, BRRI.

Seedling ht (cm)	Seedling ^a color rate (A)	Seedling strength (mg dry matter/cm) (B)	Seedling quality	
			(A) (B)	Index
11.1	5	8.97	44.9	100
11.1	5	7.57	37.8	84
10.1	4	5.51	22.0	49
10.3	4	4.11	16.4	36
9.2	2	6.33	12.7	28
8.9	2	4.20	8.4	18
9.0	1	3.50	3.5	8
9.8	1	2.65	2.55	6

^a 5-1 : deep green - yellow.

Table 2. Relationships among seedling quality and grain yield, growth duration, and seedling strength. BRRI.

Season	Variety	Correlation coefficient ^a		
		Yield	Growth duration (days)	Seedling strength
Boro, 1980	BR3	-.522	-.727*	.927**
	BR7	-.006	-.233	.965**
Boro, 1981	BR3	.678	-.838**	.901**
	BR9	.376	-.834**	.963**
Aus, 1981	BR3	.439	-.305	.894**
Aman, 1981	BR4	.529	-.845**	.990**

^a *significant at .05 level; **significant at .01 level.

Effect of planting time and density on yields of short-duration rice varieties

R. C. Gautam and K. C. Sharma, Agronomy Department, College of Agriculture, G. B. Pant University of Agriculture and Technology, Pantnagar 263145, U.P., India

Field experiments during the kharif (wet) season 1975-77 at the Crop Research Centre (29° N lat, 79.3 E long, 243.84 m altitude) explored the effect of